

Preliminary Results from Smart Integrated Devices for Telemedicine to Combat COVID-19 Toward New Resilience City - Smart4COV19/Telemedicine Project

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Abstract: The primary goal of this research is to create a health integration system for the swift identification of COVID-19 and similar pandemic infections. Given the rapid transmission rate of this disease, it's crucial to develop advanced technology to prevent human-to-human transmission. This system incorporates a 3D tool that utilizes a combination of GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) on smartphones, affordable GNSS, and LIDAR. These components generate a smart 3D city model for tracking individual information, accessible via a smartphone app linked with GNSS positioning and a COVID-19 spatial database. Additionally, the system includes environmental monitoring to assess the correlation between weather, air pollution, and COVID-19 risk. Telemedicine via smartphones can mitigate these risks by providing support to mildly ill patients, reducing their exposure to COVID-19 cases. The results of models for converting TROPOMI – S5p aerosol data to PM concentrations over Burgas, Bulgaria are also outlined.

Предварителни резултати от Интелигентни интегрирани устройства за телемедицина за борба с COVID-19 към нови устойчиви градове - Smart4COV19/Проект за телемедицина

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Резюме: Основната цел на това изследване е създаването на система за интеграция в здравеопазването за бързо откриване на COVID-19 и подобни пандемични инфекции. Поради бързината на разпространение на тази болест, е от съществено значение да се разработи напреднала технология за предотвратяване на човек-на-човек предаване. Тази система включва 3D инструмент, който използва комбинация от GNSS (система за глобално навигационно спътниково устройство) на смартфони, достъпни GNSS и LIDAR. Тези компоненти генерират интелигентен 3D градски модел за проследяване на индивидуална информация, достъпен чрез приложение за смартфон, свързано с GNSS позициониране и пространствена база данни за COVID-19. Освен това, системата включва мониторинг на околната среда, за да се оцени връзката между времето, замърсяването на въздуха и риска от COVID-19. Телемедицината чрез смартфони може да намали тези рискове, като осигури подкрепа на леко заболяващи пациенти и намали тяхната експозиция на случаи на COVID-19. Резултатите от моделите за преобразуване на TROPOMI – S5p данни за аерозоли в концентрации на PM над Бургас, България, също са онагледени.

Introduction

In the face of the COVID-19 pandemic, the integration of innovative technology with healthcare has emerged as a crucial avenue to address the challenges posed by the virus. Smart Integrated Devices for Telemedicine represent a cutting-edge approach aimed at combating COVID-19 while fostering the evolution of resilient urban landscapes. This interdisciplinary fusion of telemedicine and technological advancements not only seeks to swiftly identify and manage infections but also aims to lay the groundwork for a more robust, responsive city infrastructure. This introduction delves into the pivotal role of these smart integrated devices in reshaping healthcare delivery, enhancing disease surveillance, and fortifying cities against the ongoing and future pandemics. The main aim of this study is to establish a healthcare integration system for swift identification of COVID-19 and analogous pandemic infections. Due to the rapid spread of this disease, the development of sophisticated technology to prevent person-to-person transmission is imperative. This system incorporates a 3D tool utilizing a blend of GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) on smartphones, cost-effective GNSS, and LIDAR. These components generate a sophisticated 3D city model to track individual data, accessible through a smartphone app linked with GNSS positioning and a COVID-19 spatial database. Furthermore, the system conducts environmental monitoring to evaluate the relationship between weather patterns, air quality, and the risk of COVID-19 transmission. Noteworthy is the heightened susceptibility of specific demographics, such as individuals with chronic non-communicable diseases and pregnant women, who often face severe complications from COVID-19. Telemedicine via smartphones serves to mitigate these risks by providing assistance to mildly ill patients, reducing their exposure to COVID-19 cases. The model's efficacy is assessed by comparing it with observational data and models from the Copernicus CAMS¹ service. Additionally, the study outlines the results of models converting TROPOMI–S5p aerosol data to PM concentrations specifically over Burgas, Bulgaria. Similarly, previous national urban air quality models were implemented before [1-5].

Fig. 1. Schematic Overview of the Research Project Structure

(Note: WG = Working Group, Bold line = Research Pathways, Dashed line = Connection among WG)

¹ <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/cams-nrealtime/levtype=sfc/>,
<https://www.regional.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/>

Fig. 2. Expected output of the research: 3D Modelling for tracing people and safe flight plan

Diseases characterized by high rates of transmission necessitate technological solutions capable of contact tracing, utilizing affordable GNSS receivers, GNSS-enabled smartphones, and LIDAR. These technologies aim to collect and analyze individual data, deciphering human interactions and the patterns of disease propagation. The approach of a 3D city model for disaster management involves mapping zones based on structures, assessing their potential for disease dissemination. This method offers a comprehensive evaluation, considering multiple factors like hazard, vulnerability, and capacity. The hazard index is calculated based on COVID-19 clusters and crowded areas (points of interest), such as shopping centers, markets, banks, offices, educational institutions, transportation hubs like airports or terminals, and commercial or industrial districts. Evaluating vulnerability relies on parameters encompassing physical, social, and psychological conditions that influence people's ability to prepare for and respond to hazards. Capacity assessment is rooted in spatial parameters within the 3D city model, including public health service coverage, capacity, and transport facilities linked with designated health centers handling COVID-19 cases. Weighted analysis of these parameters determines the potential disease spread risk and strategies for mitigation. Through an intuitive Android application integrated with GNSS positioning, user-friendly access to patient locations and potential risks is enabled, prompting community-based preventive measures. Additionally, this system provides information on medical waste disposal locations, aiding in monitoring and proper disposal practices.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, viruses often follow patterns tied to specific weather conditions, temperatures, and air pollution levels characteristic of an area. This research employs an analytical approach to spatial statistical remote sensing, aiming to optimize the prevention strategies against virus transmission. The study focuses on analysing CO₂ and reflectance temperature components and their relationship with pandemics, incorporating data collection of PM 2.5 and PM 10. This system is designed to identify regions where weather conditions might make disease transmission more likely.

Fig. 3. Integrated Smart Devices Development Based on Multi Sensor for Telemedicine to Combat Covid19 toward New Resilience City

As part of the project, the Indonesian partner aims to create a health integration system capable of swiftly identifying not only COVID-19 infected individuals but also similar pandemic diseases. Simultaneously, they intend to develop smart devices for emergency responses to COVID-19 situations. This system's objective is to detect weather patterns, temperatures, and air composition in regions associated with the onset of pandemics. To fortify this system, a 3D city model based on LiDAR data is incorporated to aid in flight planning and mobile data tracking, identifying gathering points and

residences to assess the potential for person-to-person transmission. Integrated sensor equipment, including heart rate, O₂, and temperature sensors, will transmit real-time data for community health assessments. The diagnosis of COVID-19 and other pandemic diseases will be supported by the development of a digital ES Scan sensor, facilitating lung condition analysis whose data will be sent to a server for thorough analysis. Additionally, a medical drone will be constructed to deliver swabs, medications, medical tools, and test data.

The implementation of an optimized digital platform for the health integration system can be executed in locations equipped with medicines, hospital beds, and specialized medical professionals adept in disease management. This approach aims to prevent patient accumulation in specific facilities. Additionally, this research endeavors to create an integrated sensor employing a pulse oximeter to assess patient temperature, heart rate, and oxygen levels—critical parameters used in diagnosing COVID-19 cases. This sensor is linked to a system capable of transmitting gathered data to a server for analysis.

Presently, CT-SCAN technology is utilized to assess the lung conditions of COVID-19 patients. However, its drawbacks include immobility (lack of portability) and high cost. Moreover, due to the interaction between infected patients and the CT scanning device, there's an increased risk of potential virus transmission. To address these limitations, this study proposes an alternative with the development of an Electromagnetic Scattering Scanning (ES-SCAN). This innovative solution offers affordability, portability, ease of maintenance, and low power consumption. Additionally, an UltraViolet (UV) disinfectant chamber will be designed to sterilize all existing medical devices in use.

Materials and methods

The work embedded within the project is related to gathering data about the quality of atmospheric air. For this purpose, the project team is focused on the largest network for monitoring atmospheric air quality – IQair. This network is expanding globally with private investments, where each installed and compatible sensor can link to the system's network, aiming to provide more accurate and timely information about the state of atmospheric air. The stations provided by IQair come in two types. The installation of multiple AirVisual Series Outdoor stations and their connection to the international sensor network of IQair aims to deliver more detailed and precise information about atmospheric pollution.

Sofia and Burgas were chosen for this study due to distinct reasons. Sofia, as the largest city, mirrors certain aspects of Surabaya, Indonesia, making it a fitting comparative model. With over 5 monitoring stations providing comprehensive data on atmospheric pollutants and the progression of SARS-2 (COVID-19), Sofia stands as a major emitter of atmospheric pollutants. On the other hand, Burgas, while contributing to atmospheric pollution, presents a different pollution profile, offering a valuable comparison with Sofia for novel insights. Burgas faces well-documented environmental concerns regarding air quality, especially monitored by the Regional Inspectorate for Environment and Water (RIEW) Burgas, primarily due to intermittent emissions from the Lukoil oil refinery, a significant polluter challenging to track due to its sporadic nature.

Respiratory ailments often trace back to fine particulate matter, particularly PM 2.5. However, few air quality monitoring stations in Bulgaria measure this parameter, with only Sofia and Varna having a single AQM station for PM 2.5 measurement.

Burgas initiated an air quality improvement project (<http://87.126.141.158/burgas/>) operating a mobile station. Under these circumstances, it might be more beneficial to strengthen the national monitoring network (<http://www.eea.government.bg/kav/>) in a different region.

This study focuses on Burgas' central urban area, with only one AQM station situated there. Data from 5 AQM stations in Sofia and additional information from the Kopitoto station are also included in this study.

Data from 5 air quality monitoring stations in Sofia and 1 in Burgas has been gathered continuously from January 1, 2020, up to the present day. This information encompasses hourly readings for NO₂, CO, and PM₁₀, and from one Sofia station, PM_{2.5} data is also included. The primary source for this data is the European Environment Agency. Additionally, meteorological data for both cities has been compiled daily since the beginning of 2021, covering temperature, wind speed, and precipitation, drawn from various sources. Furthermore, satellite data for NO₂ and CO in graphical and numerical formats has been collected from Sentinel-5P since January 1, 2020, sourced from TEMIS and the Sentinel-5P Pre-Operations Data Hub² [6]. Information on the spread of SARS-2 has been gathered from June 6, 2020, onwards, detailing daily total and active cases for Sofia, Sofia Region, Burgas, and the country as a whole, acquired from the Ministry of Health and Regional Health Inspectorates [7].

² <https://s5phub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home>

Air quality monitoring with the IQAir system for Burgas

The Local Air Quality Management System of the city of Burgas (LAQMS) was developed at SRTI-BAS based on 12 IQAir Visual outdoor stations.

The locations for installing the sensors have been chosen to ensure maximum coverage in all residential areas of the city, including the central part of the sea garden. The system measures smoke (PM1), fine dust (PM2.5), coarse dust (PM10), temperature, relative humidity and barometric pressure. The system has Dual PM sensor design for added accuracy and reliability. High accuracy of the AirVisual Outdoor has been verified by the Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology (METAS) (<https://www.iqair.com/air-quality-monitors>).

A-1

A-2

B-1

B-2

Fig. 4. Figure 4 shows the mounting of two of the sensors respectively „A-1, A-2“ Meden Rudnik district and „B-1, B-2“ Slaveykov district.

Development of a geodatabase model

A geodatabase model has been developed based on reference data, satellite data (meteorological data, atmospheric pollution data), COVID-19 morbidity data, and ground-level measurements. The schema of the geodatabase in the ArcGIS Pro environment is provided in Figure 5. The geodatabase contains georeferenced layers with information on meteorological parameters, atmospheric pollution, and COVID-19 morbidity. The data stored in the geodatabase are visualized across a series of maps, offering a visual representation of the information stored in the database.

Fig. 5. Structure of the geodatabase for the city of Burgas

A visualization of some of the database data is provided in Fig. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6. COV-19 cases (above)³ and air pollution in Dolno Ezerovo (below)⁴

³ COV-19 data - <https://data.egov.bg/data/resourceView/cb5d7df0-3066-4d7a-b4a1-ac26525e0f0c>

⁴ System for informing the population about ambient air quality <https://www.eea.europa.eu/kav/> and Europe AIS - <https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/air/air-quality-index;>
<https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/map/fme/AirQualityExport.htm>

Fig. 7. Aerosol index from Sentinel-5P, obtained from the shooting on 06 June 2023

Conclusions

The Smart4COV19 initiative focuses on utilizing satellite-derived atmospheric chemistry data to enhance air pollution modeling and urban-scale air quality management. The aim is to evaluate the spatial distribution of surface particulate matter concentrations. This was accomplished through a fusion of diverse models (including meteorological and statistical models), data from satellite-mounted instruments like TROPOMI-S5p, and observations of air quality from ground-based sources.

The technology developed for Burgas holds potential for implementation in other Bulgarian cities. The algorithms created can also be customized to accommodate data from alternative satellite instruments with higher spatial resolution. This adaptation could facilitate data assimilation in smaller regions or be replicated in different urban centers.

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